

Addressing Sensory Sensitivity: Strategies to Support a Student Avoiding Music and Energizer Activities

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Abstract. Sensory sensitivity is a common concern among young children and can affect their participation in classroom activities, especially those involving music and movement. This study aimed to identify sensory sensitivity among preschool learners and determine strategies that can support a student who avoids music and energizer activities. The study was conducted at Katipunan Child Development Center in Quezon City using a descriptive quantitative research design. Participants included ten parents of students aged 4–5 years old and one classroom teacher. Data were collected through a researcher made questionnaire covering demographic profile, sensory sensitivity, response to music and energizer activities, and coping and support strategies, using a five-point Likert scale. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and weighted mean were used to analyze the data. Findings showed that students displayed sensory sensitivity at times, particularly toward loud sounds and high energy activities, which led to hesitation, anxiety, and avoidance during music and energizer routines. Both parents and the teacher observed improved participation when coping strategies such as providing quiet space, giving advance warnings, using visual cues, and offering alternative tasks were applied. The study emphasizes the importance of understanding sensory sensitivity and using simple, supportive classroom strategies to help young learners feel safe, included, and more comfortable in participating in daily school activities.

Keywords: Sensory sensitivity, Kindergarten, Music activities, Energizer activities, Coping strategies

Introduction

Sensory Sensitivity is a common challenge among young learners, especially those who are still developing their ability to manage sounds and movement. In early childhood settings, many classrooms use music and energizer tasks to make learning fun and active, but not all children respond to these activities in the same way. This kind of response points to sensory sensitivity, a condition where a child may feel stressed or uncomfortable during group routines.

Understanding this behavior helps teachers to find ways to support the student students so they feel safe and included during class activities. Several studies explain how children with sensory sensitivities may struggle to tolerate loud or unpredictable sounds, which can affect their comfort and participation in school routines. Studies on TOMATIS auditory training demonstrate that structured sound stimulation can improve sound stimulation, attention, and emotional regulation among children with sensory processing challenges, particularly those sensitive to auditory input (Fu et al., 2024). Similarly, research on improvisational music therapy highlights that predictable and child-led musical experiences help reduce anxiety and support engagement, making sound-based activities more manageable for children with sensory sensitivities (Jaschke et al., 2024).

Sensory sensitivity also influences how children adapt to everyday noise in the classroom. Cognitive sound exposure therapy provides evidence that gradual and guided exposure to sound can lower hypersensitivity and help children adjust more comfortably to daily auditory environments (Thieren et al., 2024). In addition, a systematic review of music therapy found that structured music interventions enhance a children's social responses and emotional adjustment, showing how music can be used in supportive ways for learners with sensory needs (Ke et al., 2022). Recent experimental studies also show the repetitive and predictable musical patterns have a calming effect on children with sensory sensitivities, helping reduce anxiety and promoting positive engagement during activities that involve sound (Kim et al., 2024).

Even with these findings, few studies focus on how children respond to sound and how music interventions can support sensory needs, little research directly examines how teachers can assist a student who avoids music and energizer activities in a typical early childhood classroom. Most specialized intervention studies are conducted in controlled environments, which do not fully reflect the daily realities of class routines, peer interactions, and cultural expectations in school settings. In response to this gap, this study aims to identify practical and developmentally appropriate strategies that teachers can use to support a student who avoids music and energizer activities due to sensory sensitivity. By integrating evidence from auditory and music-related research with observed classroom experiences, the study seeks to offer a clearer understanding of how sensory sensitivity affects a child's daily activities at Katipunan Child Development Center. The study included the views of ten parents and one teacher. The findings aim to help teachers, parents, and early childhood programs understand how to support the child so they can feel safe, join activities, and take part in class with more comfort and confidence.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The study used a descriptive quantitative research design to determine and analyze how sensory sensitivity affects the child's way of joining music and energizer activities. All variables were observed in their natural setting and not manipulated.

Participants

The participants consisted of 10 students aged 4–5 from Katipunan Child Development Center in Quezon City. The respondents were 10 parents and 1 teacher. They were chosen

through purposive sampling since their teachers know which students showed signs of sensory sensitivity. Only parents or guardians who were directly taking care of the child were included.

Instruments

The study used a researcher made questionnaire with four sections. These sections covered the demographic profile, sensory sensitivity, response to music and energizer activities, and coping and support strategies. A five-point Likert scale from Always (5) to Never (1) was used. Experts reviewed the questionnaire and a pilot test was done to make sure the items were easy to understand.

Procedure

The researchers created the instrument, secured expert review, revised items where needed, and coordinated with the daycare center for the data gathering. Then surveys were given to the respondents and later collected for coding and analysis.

Data Analysis

The responses were encoded, counted, and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Frequency and percentage were used to describe the respondents' profile, while weighted means were used to identify the students' sensory sensitivity, response to music and energizer activities, and their response to coping and support strategies. Microsoft Excel was used to compute and organize the data. The results were shown in tables and used to explain the findings.

Results

Table 1

Age of Parent Respondents (n=10)

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20 years old and below	0	0
21-30 years old	4	40
31-40 years old	3	30
41-50 years old	3	30
51 years old and above	0	0
Total:	10	100%

Most parent respondents belonged to the 21 – 40 age group, indicating that the majority were young to middle-aged adults.

Table 2

Gender of Parent Respondents (n=10)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Female	10	100
Male	0	0
Total:	10	100%

All parent respondents were female, indicating the mothers participated in the study.

Table 3
Educational Attainment of Parent Respondents (n=10)

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Undergraduate	6	60
Vocational Graduate	2	20
Bachelor's Degree	2	20
Master's Degree	0	0
Total:	10	100%

Parents had varied educational backgrounds, with most being undergraduate and some having vocational or bachelor's degrees.

Table 4
Demographic of Teacher Respondent (n=1)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	51 years old and above	1	100
Gender	Female	1	100
Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	1	100
Total:		1	100%

The teacher respondent was a female aged 51 years and above with a bachelor's degree, providing experienced classroom observations.

Table 5
Summary of Parents' Responses on Sensory Sensitivity, Response to Music and Energizer Activities, and Coping and Support Strategies

Variable	Key Indicators	Summary	Interpretation
Sensory Sensitivity	Reaction to sound and noise	Sensitivity to loud sounds; discomfort occurs at times	Moderate sensory sensitivity
Response to Music and Energizer Activities	Anxiety, avoidance, participation	Prefer quiet activities; avoids music and energizers at times	Low-moderate response
Coping and Support Strategies	Quiet space, visual cues, sensory tools, alternative tasks, advance warnings	Calms faster with quiet space, alternative tasks, and clear preparation	Moderate response

Parents observed that the students in the study showed sensitivity at times, particularly during music and high- energy activities. Several students preferred quiet activities and avoided music and energizer activities occasionally. Parents noted that students became calmer and participated better when provided with quiet space and advance warnings.

Table 6
Summary of Teacher Responses on Sensory Sensitivity, Response to Music and Energizer Activities, and Coping and Support Strategies

Variable	Key Indicators	Summary	Interpretation
Sensory Sensitivity	Reaction to sound and noise	Notices sensitivity to loud sounds and music	Sometimes Observed
Response to Music and Energizer Activities	Anxiety, avoidance, participation	Shows hesitation and limited participation in music and energizers	Sometimes Observed
Coping and Support Strategies	Quiet space, visual cues, sensory tools, alternative tasks, advance warnings	Responds better when given quiet space, alternative tasks and clear preparation	Sometimes Observed

The teacher observed that the students in the study showed sensory sensitivity at times, especially during music and energizer activities. Some students hesitated and participated less during noisy or high energy activities. Providing quiet and clear preparation helped improve the students’ participation and response.

Discussion

The presence of sensory sensitivity among the participating preschool learners reflects common challenges in early childhood classrooms that use music and energizer activities as part of daily routines. The students in the study displayed sensory sensitivities in loud sound and high energy routines sometimes observed by the teacher and parents aligns with sound sensitivity often experience stress and discomfort when exposed to loud or unpredictable auditory environments (Thieren et al., 2024). However, coping and support strategies gained positive responds of the students. The student’s calmness improved when they were given quiet space, advance warnings, and clear preparation that supports the structured sound exposure as used in TOMATIS auditory training (Fu et al., 2024). Similarly, (Jaschke et al., 2024) emphasized that predictable and child-centered musical experiences reduce anxiety and increase engagement, which reflects the improved responses observed in this study. The effectiveness of quiet space, alternative tasks, and clear preparation observed in this study reflects evidence that environmental adjustment can support children’s emotional and social participation during sound-based activities (Ke et al., 2022).

The findings highlight a clear relationship between sensory sensitivity and coping strategies. While loud and high energy activities may initially cause discomfort, appropriate support strategies help students respond more positively. This reflects broader findings that

classroom environments and adult guidance can either increase or reduce sensory stress depending on how activities are managed. This study provides local evidence to early childhood settings by showing simple support strategies used by parents and teachers help sensory sensitive learners feel included and participate better in classroom activities.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study concludes that the 4–5-year-old students at Katipunan Child Development Center showed sensory sensitivity at times, particularly during music and energizer activities. Both parents and the teacher observed that loud sounds and high-energy activities sometimes caused discomfort, hesitation, and avoidance. However, the findings also showed that the use of coping and support strategies such as providing quiet space, advance warnings, visual cues, alternative tasks and clear preparation helped students calm down and participate better. These results highlight the importance of understanding sensory sensitivity and using appropriate support strategies to promote inclusion in early childhood classrooms.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that teachers continue to use structured and predictable routines when conducting music and energizer activities. Providing quiet space, clear instructions, giving alternative tasks and advance preparation can help sensory-sensitive learners feel more comfortable and engaged. Parents are encouraged to apply similar strategies at home to support their child’s emotional regulation and response to sound-related activities. The daycare center may consider conducting orientations or sharing guidelines with parents on supporting children with sensory sensitivities. Future studies may include a larger number of participants, use direct classroom observations, or explore other strategies that support sensory-sensitive learners in early childhood settings.

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